

D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP2.1

Protocol for Water Sampling

**Version 1
May/2020**

1. Description of the catchment areas in the different countries

1.1 . Austria

At the Hydrology Open Air Laboratory (HOAL) catchment area in Petzenkirchen (**fig 1**), water samples from compartments 5 (field drainage), 6 (surface/river water) and 7 (ground water, the same used as for the pigs at farm A) will be collected four times within the 1-year sampling.

Fig. 1. Overview of the catchment area at Petzenkirchen and selected monitoring stations for water sampling.

The **river (stream)** has a length of 620 m. The selected water monitoring station is located at the stream. It consists of a device called “H-Flume”, which serves to measure the water level and the flow rate. The outflow of that H-Flume ensures an even distribution of the flow over the entire measuring width.

The **wastewater treatment plant** is a small biological treatment plant connected with the HOAL. It is used for purification of domestic wastewater and wastewater from hotels, restaurants, sports facilities, shops and other nearby places before discharge into a receiving watercourse or rainwater channel or before infiltration. Water sampling

is only possible in the effluent (clean water which flows out of the treatment plant).

1.2 Portugal

In Portugal, water samples will be collected from compartments 5 (field drainage), 6 (surface/river water), 7 (groundwater, and drinking water used at pigs farm), and 10 (wastewater treatment plant). Samples will be collected four times within the 1-year sampling, one each season.

Fig. 2. Overview of the catchment area at Santarém, Portugal, and selected monitoring stations for water sampling.

At the Portuguese HOAL (fig 2), the wastewater treatment is performed in three **waste stabilization ponds (WSPs)**. Wastewater or "influent" enters on one side of the WSP and exits on the other side as "effluent", after spending several days in the pond, during which natural treatment processes take place. Regarding compartment 10, water sampling will be performed in the WSP1 influent (wastewater from a collection tank) and WSP2 effluent (prior to discharge into receiving waters). WSP1 will be considered as a sedimentation tank and water will be collected at the surface.

Groundwater will be sampled from a borehole of 208 meters deep. Sampling is only possible through a tap connected to a submerged pump at a depth of 190 meters. Groundwater is also pumped into a tank and chemically treated, which is afterward distributed to animals and farmers (**drinking water**).

Field drainage water will be sampled near the borehole, in the influent water of a tank

that naturally collects water from the upper neighboring fields.

For **Surface/river water** sampling, WSP3 effluent (clean water that flows out of the pond directly to a water line) will be collected.

1.3 . Czech Republic

In Czech Republic, water samples will be collected from compartments 6 (surface/river water) and 7 (drinking water/groundwater). Samples will be collected four times within the 1-year sampling, one each season. Surface water will be collected from a stream which is located about 270 m from the field fertilized with manure.

1.4 . Estonia

In Estonia, water samples will be collected from compartments 5 (field drainage), 6 (surface/river water), 7 (groundwater), and 10 (wastewater treatment plant). Samples will be collected four times within the 1-year sampling, one each season.

1.5 Ireland

In Ireland, we will collect samples from municipal sewage treatment plant in Mutton Island, which treats sewage waste from a population of approximately 170,000 people from Galway City and surrounding area. This WWTP was upgraded in 2015 for increased capacity for sewage treatment using a non-nitrifying process. Samples to be collected from Mutton Island will include influent, sedimentation tank, sewage sludge and effluent.

Fig. 3. Mutton Island WWTP in Galway city, Ireland.

2. Equipment

- Pump device for groundwater collection
- Bailer sampler of 250ml for wastewater collection
- Sludge Judge for wastewater collection
- Marker (water resistant)
- Disinfectant (sodium hypochlorite- Danklorix -10%)
- Storage box (with cooling ice packs) or similar (4-8°C).
- Four types of water containers for:
 - Microbiological and molecular analysis: 500 mL sterile PET containers with Sodium Thiosulfate (120mg/L).
 - Elements Analysis: 100 mL PET (polyethylene terephthalate) sterile bottles pre-filled with nitric acid.
 - Herbicides: aluminium 250 mL bottles or 250 PET (polyethylene terephthalate) bottles.
 - Antibiotics quantification: Dark (UV-protected) 200 mL bottles of polypropylene (alternatively, use aluminium film to cover them).
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3. Procedure

3.1 . Volume and distribution

For each water compartment, the overall volume (sum of the volume of all containers) should be no less than 2L as distributed in **table 1**. Note that before collection at the field, each of the tubes intended for element analysis must be acidified in the laboratory with two drops of concentrated nitric acid (HNO₃, for trace metal analysis grade).

Table 1. Distribution and transport conditions for water samples.

Analysis	Task	Minimum volume (ml)	Container	Transport
Antibiotics (WP4)	4.2	150	PET sterile dark bottles	-20 °C
Elements (WP4)	4.7	50	PET sterile bottles with nitric acid	4 °C
Herbicides (WP4)	4.6	200	PP or PET bottles	
Microbiology (WP2 and WP3)	2.3, 2.4, 3.1	500	PET sterile bottles with tiosulfate	

3.2 . Compartment 5: Field drainage

If H-Flume devices (Fig. 3) are available (e.g: Austria):

- Put on sterile gloves
- Fill the desired container, empty it and fill it again just above the line (except the one for microbiology analysis, which it is just filled once).
- Do not insert leaves, stones or wooden sticks inside.
- Tighten the lid completely to avoid spillage during shipping and secure containers for elements analysis with Parafilm®.
- Label the bottle with its corresponding sample ID.
- Transport under conditions displayed in **Table 1** never surpass 10°C.
- Upon arrival to the laboratory and taking into account the water volumes in **figure 6**, process samples immediately for each type of analysis. If this is not possible, keep refrigerated up to 1 day the microbiological container and freeze at -20 the other containers.

Fig. 3. H-Flume

Sampling from a water-pouring spout (e.g: Portugal, Ireland):

- Put on sterile gloves.
- Clean the water-pouring spout with a clean cloth to wipe the outlet and to remove any dirt.
- Let the water run for 1-2 minutes.
- Remove the gloves and put others sterile.
- Fill the desired container, empty it and fill it again just above the line (except the one for microbiology analysis, which it is just filled once).
- Do not insert leaves, stones or wooden sticks inside.
- Tighten the lid completely to avoid spillage during shipping and secure containers for elements analysis with Parafilm®.
- Label the bottle with its corresponding sample ID.
- Transport under conditions displayed in **Table 1** never surpass 10°C.
- Upon arrival to the laboratory and taking into account the water volumes in **figure 6**, process samples immediately for each type of analysis. If this is not possible, keep refrigerated up to 1 day the microbiological container and freeze at -20 the other containers.

3.3. Compartment 6: Surface water/River

If H-Flume devices (fig. 3) are available (e.g: Austria):

- Put on sterile gloves
- Fill the desired container, empty it and fill it again just above the line (except the one for microbiology analysis, which it is just filled once).
- Do not insert leaves, stones or wooden sticks inside.
- Tighten the lid completely to avoid spillage during shipping and secure containers for elements analysis with Parafilm®.

- Label the bottle with its corresponding sample ID.
- Transport under conditions displayed in **Table 1** never surpass 10°C.
- Upon arrival to the laboratory and taking into account the water volumes in **figure 6**, process samples immediately for each type of analysis. If this is not possible, keep refrigerated up to 1 day the microbiological container and freeze at -20 the other containers.

Sampling from a water-pouring spout (e.g: Portugal):

- Put on sterile gloves.
- Clean the water-pouring spout with a clean cloth to wipe the outlet and to remove any dirt.
- Desinfect the the water-pouring spout with alcohol 70%.
- Let the water run for 1-2 minutes.
- Remove the gloves and put others sterile.
- Fill the desired container, empty it and fill it again just above the line (except the one for microbiology analysis, which it is just filled once).
- Do not insert leaves, stones or wooden sticks inside.
- Tighten the lid completely to avoid spillage during shipping and secure containers for elements analysis with Parafilm®.
- Label the bottle with its corresponding sample ID.
- Transport under conditions displayed in **Table 1** never surpass 10°C.
- Upon arrival to the laboratory and taking into account the water volumes in **figure 6**, process samples immediately for each type of analysis. If this is not possible, keep refrigerated up to 1 day the microbiological container and freeze at -20 the other containers.

3.4. Compartment 7: Ground water

Sampling ground water with a pump (e.g: Austria):

- Put on sterile gloves
- Decontaminate the pump and other water sampling equipment before each use.
- Use a pump device to pump three times the lowering funnel fountain (Fig. 4).
- Fill the desired container, empty it and fill it again just above the line (except the one for microbiology analysis, which it is just filled once).
- Tighten the lid completely to avoid spillage during shipping and secure

- containers for elements analysis with Parafilm®.
- Label the bottle with its corresponding sample ID.
- Transport under conditions displayed in **Table 1** never surpass 10°C.
- Upon arrival to the laboratory and taking into account the water volumes in **figure 6**, process samples immediately for each type of analysis. If this is not possible, keep refrigerated up to 1 day the microbiological container and freeze at -20 the other containers.

Fig. 4. Pump

Sampling drinking and ground water from a tap or pump outlet (Portugal):

- Put on sterile gloves or wash hands with alcohol 70%.
- Use a clean cloth soaked with alcohol 70% to wipe the outlet and remove any dirt. Remove any attachments that may cause splashing from the tap. These attachments are a frequent source of contamination that may influence the perceived quality of the water supply.
- Sterilize the tap for 2-3 minutes (flame from a gas burner, or an alcohol-soaked cotton wool swab).
- Open the tap before sampling. Carefully turn on the tap and allow water to flow at maximum rate for 5-10 seconds, and after reduce the rate. Do not adjust the flow after it has been set.
- Fill the bottle up to about 2 cm from the top of the neck: carefully remove the cap and protective cover from the bottle, taking care to prevent entry of dust that may contaminate the sample. Hold the bottle immediately under the water jet to fill it. A small air space should be left to allow mixing before analysis. Never touch the inside of the cap or the neck of the bottle. Recap the bottle immediately.
- Tighten the lid completely to avoid spillage during shipping and secure containers for elements analysis with Parafilm®.
- Label the bottle with its corresponding sample ID.
- Transport under conditions displayed in **Table 1** never surpass 10°C.
- Upon arrival to the laboratory and taking into account the water volumes in **figure 6**, process samples immediately for each type of analysis. If this is not possible, keep refrigerated up to 1 day the microbiological container and freeze

at -20 the other containers.

3.5. Compartment 10: Wastewater

Biological wastewater treatment plant (e.g: Austria)

- Put on sterile gloves
- Submerge the bailer (Fig. 5) in the water until water flows on the top into the bailer sampler.
- Fill the desired container, empty it and fill it again just above the line (except the one for microbiology analysis, which it is just filled once).
- Tighten the lid completely to avoid spillage during shipping and secure containers for elements analysis with Parafilm[®].
- Label the bottle with its corresponding sample ID.
- Transport under conditions displayed in **Table 1** never surpass 10°C.
- Upon arrival to the laboratory and taking into account the water volumes in **figure 6**, process samples immediately for each type of analysis. If this is not possible, keep refrigerated up to 1 day the microbiological container and freeze at -20 the other containers.

Fig. 3. Bailer

Biological waste stabilization ponds (e.g: Portugal; Ireland)

- Influent, effluent and sedimentation tank water:
 - Put on sterile gloves.
 - Carefully remove the cap and protective cover from the bottle, taking

care to prevent entry of dust that may contaminate the sample.

- Fill the bottle: hold the bottle near its bottom and submerge it with pool water sample holder to a depth of about 20 cm, with the mouth facing slightly downwards. If there is a current, the bottle mouth should face towards the current. Turn the bottle upright to fill it. Replace the bottle cap.
 - Label the bottle with its corresponding sample ID.
 - Transport under conditions displayed in **Table 1** never surpass 10°C.
 - Upon arrival to the laboratory and taking into account the water volumes in **figure 6**, process samples immediately for each type of analysis. If this is not possible, keep refrigerated up to 1 day the microbiological container and freeze at -20 the other containers.
- Sewage sludge: collect five equidistant single sludge subsamples (100 g each) from a randomized grid-like pattern, then composite the collected samples. For each sample:
- Slowly lower the Sludge Judge to the bottom of the lagoon.
 - The sludge sampler's float valve opens, allowing materials to flow in. When the bottom has been reached and the pipe has filled to the surface level, tug slightly on the rope as the unit is raised. This sets the sludge sampler's check valve, trapping the mixture inside.
 - The Sludge Judge is removed clear of the material and the material released by touching a pin extending from the bottom section against a hard surface.
 - Transfer the sample to a non-metallic container. To release the material, touch the pin extending from the bottom section against a hard surface. This opens the sludge sampler's check valve to drain the sample.
 - Label the bottle with its corresponding sample ID.
 - Transport under conditions displayed in **Table 1** never surpass 10°C.
 - Upon arrival to the laboratory and taking into account the water volumes in **figure 6**, process samples immediately for each type of analysis. If this is not possible, keep refrigerated up to 1 day the microbiological container and freeze at -20 the other containers.

Figure 6. Workflow representing the volume of water needed for each type of analysis within the FED-AMR project.

4. Sample identifiers for water samples

The following sample identifiers will be given to the collected samples in the corresponding European Regions and will be used along the duration of the project.

Sample Reference	Description	Scheduled date
Austria		
AT20-D1	Austria, field drainage	Apr 20
AT20-D2	Austria, field drainage	Jul 20
AT21-D3	Austria, field drainage	Oct 20
AT21-D4	Austria, field drainage	Jan 21
AT20-R1	Austria, river/surface water	Apr 20
AT20-R2	Austria, river/surface water	Jul 20
AT21-R3	Austria, river/surface water	Oct 20
AT21-R4	Austria, river/surface water	Jan 21
AT20-G1	Austria, groundwater	Apr 20
AT20-G2	Austria, groundwater	Jul 20
AT21-G3	Austria, groundwater	Oct 20

AT21-G4	Austria, groundwater	Jan 21
AT20-WTP-I1	Austria, WTP influent	Apr 20
AT20-WTP-I2	Austria, WTP influent	Jul 20
AT20-WTP-I3	Austria, WTP influent	Oct 20
AT20-WTP-I4	Austria, WTP influent	Jan 21
AT20-WTP-E1	Austria, WTP effluent	Apr 20
AT20-WTP-E2	Austria, WTP effluent	Jul 20
AT20-WTP-E3	Austria, WTP effluent	Oct 20
AT20-WTP-E4	Austria, WTP effluent	Jan 21
Sample Reference	Description	Scheduled date
Portugal		
PT20-D1	Portugal, field drainage	Jul 20
PT20-D2	Portugal, field drainage	Oct 20
PT21-D3	Portugal, field drainage	Jan 21
PT21-D4	Portugal, field drainage	Apr 21
PT20-R1	Portugal, river/surface water	Jul 20
PT20-R2	Portugal, river/surface water	Oct 20
PT21-R3	Portugal, river/surface water	Jan 21
PT21-R4	Portugal, river/surface water	Apr 21
PT20-G1	Portugal, groundwater	Jul 20
PT20-G2	Portugal, groundwater	Oct 20
PT21-G3	Portugal, groundwater	Jan 21
PT21-G4	Portugal, groundwater	Apr 21
PT20-Dw1	Portugal, drinking water	Jul 20
PT20-Dw2	Portugal, drinking water	Oct 20
PT21-Dw3	Portugal, drinking water	Jan 21
PT21-Dw4	Portugal, drinking water	Apr 21
PT20-WTP-I1	Portugal, WTP influent	Jul 20
PT20-WTP-I2	Portugal, WTP influent	Oct 20
PT21-WTP-I3	Portugal, WTP influent	Jan 21
PT21-WTP-I4	Portugal, WTP influent	Apr 21
PT20-WTP-E1	Portugal, WTP effluent	Jul 20
PT20-WTP-E2	Portugal, WTP effluent	Oct 20
PT21-WTP-E3	Portugal, WTP effluent	Jan 21
PT21-WTP-E4	Portugal, WTP effluent	Apr 21
PT20-WTP-ST1	Portugal, WTP sedimentation tank	Jul 20
PT20-WTP-ST2	Portugal, WTP sedimentation tank	Oct 20

PT21-WTP-ST3	Portugal, WTP sedimentation tank	Jan 21
PT21-WTP-ST4	Portugal, WTP sedimentation tank	Apr 21
PT20-WTP-SS1	Portugal, WTP sewage sludge	Jul 20
PT20-WTP-SS2	Portugal, WTP sewage sludge	Oct 20
PT21-WTP-SS3	Portugal, WTP sewage sludge	Jan 21
PT21-WTP-SS4	Portugal, WTP sewage sludge	Apr 21

Sample Reference	Description	Scheduled date
Ireland		
IE20-WTP-I1	Ireland, WTP influent	Summer 2020
IE20-WTP-I2	Ireland, WTP influent	Autumn 2020
IE21-WTP-I3	Ireland, WTP influent	Winter 2021
IE21-WTP-I4	Ireland, WTP influent	Spring 2021
IE20-WTP-E1	Ireland, WTP effluent	Summer 2020
IE20-WTP-E2	Ireland, WTP effluent	Autumn 2020
IE21-WTP-E3	Ireland, WTP effluent	Winter 2021
IE21-WTP-E4	Ireland, WTP effluent	Spring 2021
IE20-WTP-ST1	Ireland, WTP sedimentation tank	Summer 2020
IE20-WTP-ST2	Ireland, WTP sedimentation tank	Autumn 2020
IE21-WTP-ST3	Ireland, WTP sedimentation tank	Winter 2021
IE21-WTP-ST4	Ireland, WTP sedimentation tank	Spring 2021
IE20-WTP-SS1	Ireland, WTP sewage sludge	Summer 2020
IE20-WTP-SS2	Ireland, WTP sewage sludge	Autumn 2020
IE21-WTP-SS3	Ireland, WTP sewage sludge	Winter 2021
IE21-WTP-SS4	Ireland, WTP sewage sludge	Spring 2021

Sample Reference	Description	Scheduled date
Czech Republic		
CZ20-R1	Czech Republic, river/surface water	Apr 20
CZ20-R2	Czech Republic, river/surface water	Aug 20
CZ21-R3	Czech Republic, river/surface water	Oct 20
CZ21-R4	Czech Republic, river/surface water	Dec 20
CZ20-G1	Czech Republic, groundwater	Apr 20
CZ20-G2	Czech Republic, groundwater	Aug 20
CZ21-G3	Czech Republic, groundwater	Oct 20
CZ21-G4	Czech Republic, groundwater	Dec 20
Sample Reference	Description	Scheduled date

Estonia		
EE20-D1	Estonia, field drainage	May 20
EE20-D2	Estonia, field drainage	Aug 20
EE21-D3	Estonia, field drainage	Jan 21
EE21-D4	Estonia, field drainage	Mar 21
EE20-R1	Estonia, river/surface water	May 20
EE20-R2	Estonia, river/surface water	Aug 20
EE21-R3	Estonia, river/surface water	Jan 21
EE21-R4	Estonia, river/surface water	Mar 21
EE20-G1	Estonia, groundwater	May 20
EE20-G2	Estonia, groundwater	Aug 20
EE21-G3	Estonia, groundwater	Jan 21
EE21-G4	Estonia, groundwater	Mar 21
EE20-WTP-I1	Estonia, WTP influent	May 20
EE20-WTP-I2	Estonia, WTP influent	Aug 20
EE20-WTP-I3	Estonia, WTP influent	Jan 21
EE20-WTP-I4	Estonia, WTP influent	Mar 21
EE20-WTP-E1	Estonia, WTP effluent	May 20
EE20-WTP-E2	Estonia, WTP effluent	Aug 20
EE20-WTP-E3	Estonia, WTP effluent	Jan 21
EE20-WTP-E4	Estonia, WTP effluent	Mar 21

5. References

ISO 19458 Water Quality – Sampling for Microbiological Analysis.

ISO 5667-1 – Water quality – Sampling Part 1: Guidance on the design of sampling programs and sampling techniques

ISO 5667-3 Water quality - Sampling, Part 3: Preservation and handling of water samples.

ISO 5667-5 Water quality - Sampling, Part 5: Guidance on sampling of drinking water from treatment Works and piped distribution systems.